

National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM) and Financial Inclusion-A Review

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Abstract:

The Deendayal Antodaya Yojana – National Rural Livelihood Mission (DAY-NRLM) is a flagship programme of the Ministry of Rural Development. The main objective of this programme is to alleviate rural poverty through building sustainable community institutions for the poor. The aim of the scheme is to cover in a phased manner, 9-10 crore Indian rural poor households with Self Help Groups so that by means of diversification of livelihood, quality of life can be enhanced (PIB,2024). Financial inclusion is a key component of the Mission. The objective of financial inclusion is to make rural women and their household engaged with the banking system. To achieve this aim the Mission has been engaged with commercial banks at strategic as well as operational level by conducting various workshops, consultative forums and capacity building programs. Under the above background, the paper tries to analyze importance of NRLM Self Help Group (SHG) bank linkage portal and the progress of DAY-NRLM in financial inclusion of the rural poor.

Keywords: Financial inclusion, SHGs, Livelihood, sustainability, Financial Literacy.

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1. Introduction:

The Deendayal Antodaya Yojana – National Rural Livelihood Mission (DAY-NRLM) is a flagship programme of the Ministry of Rural Development. In November 2015, the program was renamed Deen Dayal Antayodaya Yojana (DAY-NRLM). The main objective of this programme is to alleviate rural poverty through building sustainable community institutions of the poor. The aim of the scheme is to cover in a phased manner, 9-10 crore Indian rural poor households with Self Help Groups so that by means of diversification of livelihood, quality of life can be enhanced (PIB,2024). This would enable them to have sustainable livelihood opportunities through access to formal sources of finance, entitlements, and services from both public and private sectors. The Mission focuses on four core components to achieve its objectives. This includes-a) social mobilization and promotion of sustainable community institutions of the rural poor b) financial inclusion of the rural poor c) sustainable livelihood d) social inclusion, development and convergence.

As on March, 2024, DAY NRLM has its footprints in 28 states and 6 UTs, 7119 blocks and mobilized 10.04 crore rural families in 90.83 lakhs of SHGs. The SHGs have been federated into 5.04 lakh Village Organizations (VOs). During the period of March 2024, Revolving Fund (RF) of Rs.20,000 to Rs.30,000 per SHG have been provided to 50.41 lakh SHGs. Moreover, the Mission has provided a total of Rs. 34,13,173.41 lakh as Community Investment Fund (CIF) to 51.34 lakh SHGs. Under the above background, the paper tries to analyze importance of NRLM SHG bank linkage portal and the progress of DAY-NRLM in financial inclusion of the rural poor.

1. *Concept of NRLM SHG-Bank Linkage Portal*

A dedicated portal "NRLM SHG-Bank Linkage Portal", has been developed in order to monitor the progress of SHG Bank Linkage and to keep a track of repayment of bank loan by SHGs. SHGs are sharing data with the portal on monthly basis. Performance and management reports are also placed on the portal and Banks regularly monitor the progress. Other key interventions under Financial Inclusion during the year include:

a. Community Based Repayment Mechanism (CBRM):

Through the Community Based payback Mechanism, the Mission has also taken the initiative to guarantee the SHGs' timely payback. More than 45,387 Bank Sakhi have been assigned to bank branches in order to monitor repayment and enable smooth credit linking for SHGs. Additionally, over 57,843 bank branches have established the Community Based Repayment Mechanism (CBRM). CBRM includes Bank Sakhi. They serve as a liaison between SHGs and the banker. Additionally, Bank Saki assists SHGs in obtaining additional financial services from the bank and completes the necessary paperwork for loan applications, account opening, and other related transactions. Additionally, it serves as a mediator between the bank and the SHGs, resolving everything.

b. Alternate Credit Delivery Channels:

The digital infrastructure is being used more frequently. The delivery of financial services is moving toward being cashless and paperless. As of March 2024, more than 1,27,074 Sakhi have been deployed in 27 states. The government has been working to encourage less-cash transactions, and efforts are being made to educate and train SHG members on cashless payment methods. As of March 2024, the Mission has a pool of approximately 1.38 lakh women business correspondence (BCs) and is working to place one BC in each Gram Panchayat.

c. Dual Authentication:

SHG members must travel to bank branches in order to conduct business and withdraw cash, which requires a significant investment of time, effort and money for transportation. All public sector banks and 19 RRBs have authorized dual authentications after the Mission brought up the matter with the banks to let SHGs to conduct transactions at the BC level. The National Payment Corporation of India (NPCI), which has a pool of roughly 1.38 lakh women BCs as of March 2024, is also in the midst of implementing a dual authentication system that would allow SHGs to conduct business at each BC location in every Gram Panchayat.

d. Online Submission of Loan Application: In order to reduce the chore in submitting loan application by SHG members, a portal has been developed for online submission of loan applications. It has been implemented in 23 states. Efforts are also being made to digitize the bank accounts and Aadhar number of all SHG members. Till now, more than 4.04 lakhs SHG loan applications have been submitted to different banks through this channel.

e. Disbursement of Interest Subvention: Interest subvention policy on loans to SHGs has also being implemented. It is an effective mechanism to make credit available at affordable interest rate. It also ensures prompt repayment by SHG members. The interest subvention scheme has been extended to the entire district in the country. The amount of loan eligible for interest subvention has been extended up to Rs. 5 lakhs. Reserve Bank of India has issued new guidelines on Interest Subvention for the financial year 2023-24 for Public Sector Banks and Private Banks. NABARD has issued guidelines for Regional Rural Banks and Co-operative Banks.

2. Progress in the field of financial inclusion

Financial inclusion is a key component of the Mission. Financial inclusion under DAY-NRLM enables each SHGs to be linked to banks and access all financial services from the banks. The Mission also focuses on making rural women and their household engaged with the banking system. To achieve this aim the Mission has been engaged with commercial banks at strategic as well as operational level by conducting various workshops, consultative forums and capacity building programs. Financial inclusion under NRLM encourages the formation of self-help groups (SHGs) that act as conduits for channeling financial resources to these underserved areas. These SHGs receive financial literacy training, helping to instill a culture of saving and responsible financial management. With easier access to credit, rural entrepreneurs and small-scale farmers can invest in income-generating activities, leading to improved livelihoods and bolstered community resilience. During the period of 2023-24, the Mission has organized 3 important meetings to increase SHG bank linkages. DAY-NRLM focuses on both demand and supply side to promote financial inclusion. Demand side includes promotion of financial literacy among the poor. The supply side focuses on co-ordination with the banking institutions, encouragement of use of digital financial technologies, identifies and promotes SHG members as Business Correspondent Agents (BCAs) and community facilitators like Bank Sakhis. Financial literacy is one of the important strategies to keep SHGs households aware about relevant financial services. A cadre of 'Financial Literacy Community Resource Person (FL CRPs) has been developed to cater to the needs of imparting financial literacy to the rural masses. The work of the FL CRPs is to conduct regular and need based awareness camps in villages in a batch of 30 to 50 SHG members with the help of SHGs and their federations.

Progress of NRLM during the period of 2023-24:

A lot of progress can be observed in the performance of NRLM during the recent period. The table below shows the progress of NRLM during period of 2023-24.

Table 1: Progress of NRLM during the period of 2023-24

Sl. No.	Paticulars	Progress up to March 2023	Cumulative progress up to March 2024
1	Intensive blocks under implementation	7073	7119
2	Households covered (in lakh)	903.7	1000.4
3	SHGs promoted (in lakh)	83.44	90.83
4	VOs promoted (in lakh)	4.87	5.04
5	CLF promoted	31671	32439
6	SHGS provided with RF (in lakh)	44.25	50.41
7.	SHGs provided with CIF (in lakh)	39.71	51.34
8	Amount of RF disbursed	6505239	776013.41
9	Amount of CIF disbursed	2405239	3413173.41
Source: Annual Report, 2023-24, Ministry of Rural Development			

It shows the progress up to March, 2023 and cumulative progress upto March 2024. Intensive blocks under implementation increased from 7073 during 2023 to 7119 during March 2024. Similarly, it has been observed that SHGs promoted was 83.33 lakh till March 2023 while the cumulative progress of SHGs promoted was 90.83 lakhs in March 2024. A major change can be observed in SHGs provided with RF. It was 44.25 lakh in March 2023 while the cumulative progress was 51.34 during March 2024. Similarly, we can observe that, there has been an increase in all the particulars with respect to the year 2023 to 2024.

Financial progress of NRLM during the period 2024-25:

Table 2 shows the financial progress of NRLM during the period of 2024-25. The data shows that the expenditure is more than the available fund in the state of Assam. On the other hand, in the state of Andhra Pradesh, it has been observed that out of the total funds available, 31 per cent has been spent on the NRLM. It can be observed that in most of the states, percentage of expenditure is more than 60 per cent of the available funds except in the state of Andhra Pradesh (31 per cent) and Uttar Pradesh (48 per cent).

Table: 2 Percentage of expenditure against available funds			
States	Total available funds	Expenditure incurred	Percentage of expenditure against available funds
Andhra Pradesh	14123.17	4443.96	31.47
Assam	34198.05	37784.64	110.49
Bihar	230178.15	144337.84	62.71
Chhattisgarh	36133.60	27157.36	75.16
Gujarat	28286.05	21131.93	74.71
Jharkhand	69760.85	47809.95	68.53
Karnataka	34201.82	33898.10	99.11
Kerala	17162.15	11807.89	68.80
Madhya Pradesh	55128.19	34177.52	62.00
Maharashtra	115056.49	95697.12	83.17
Odisha	61670.23	40251.28	65.27
Rajasthan	42163.54	26679.43	63.28
Tamil Nadu	67142.58	41368.13	61.61
Uttar Pradesh	242760.16	115709.45	47.66
West Bengal	105110.12	77419.28	73.66

Source: Annual Report, 2024-25, Ministry of Rural Development

SHGs with and without bank account across various states of India:

Self Help Groups (SHGs) with bank accounts offer a multifaceted approach to financial inclusion and empowerment, particularly in regions where traditional banking models struggle to penetrate. A bank account also instills a sense of financial discipline and awareness among SHG members, enhancing their financial literacy. Furthermore, having a formal bank account can improve an SHG's credibility and viability, often attracting government support and non-governmental organization assistance. Table 3 shows the data on SHGs with and without bank account for the major states. The data shows that the state having highest number of SHGs having no bank account is West Bengal (19 per cent) followed by Bihar (9 per cent) and Madhya Pradesh (7 per cent). On the other hand the state having all SHGs with bank account is Andhra Pradesh followed by Kerala and Tamil Nadu.

Table 3 SHGs With and without bank account

States	Bank Account		Total Number of SHGs	Percentage of SHG with no bank account
	Having no bank account	Having bank account		
Andhra Pradesh	0	843184	343184	0
Assam	178	350343	350521	0.05
Bihar	95029	889484	984513	9.65
Chhattisgarh	7038	255276	262314	2.68
Gujarat	527	274511	275038	0.19
Jharkhand	337	279267	279604	0.12
Karnataka	1244	239741	240985	0.52
Kerala	24	245154	245178	0.01
Madhya Pradesh	34343	428250	462593	7.42
Maharashtra	2547	603500	606047	0.42
Odisha	3483	528296	532179	0.65
Rajasthan	10966	240559	251525	4.36
Tamil Nadu	98	297684	297782	0.03
Uttar Pradesh	15100	737223	770007	1.96
West Bengal	203710	1057659	1072759	18.99

Source: Annual Report, 2024-25, Ministry of Rural Development

3. Discussion and conclusion:

The National Rural Livelihood Mission is playing a vital role in improving the financial inclusion in the rural areas. However, implementing financial inclusion within the framework of the National Rural Livelihoods Mission (NRLM) presents several challenges that need to be addressed to maximize its impact on reducing rural poverty. One of the major challenges is the lack of accessible financial infrastructure in remote and rural areas. Many villages are yet to have bank branches, ATMs or other financial services, making it difficult for rural population to engage with formal financial system (Gothwal & Siwach, 2023).

Moreover, the infrastructural inadequacy is compounded by connectivity issues and poor road conditions, further isolating rural communities. Another significant challenge is the low level of financial literacy among rural inhabitants. Many individuals lack the knowledge and understanding of financial products and services, which hinders their ability to effectively participate in financial inclusion initiatives. Cultural and language barriers also play a role, as financial systems tend to operate in a manner that does not always consider regional languages and local contexts.

In recent years, the involvement of financial institutions, such as banks, has become increasingly significant. SHGs with bank accounts often experience greater financial security and credibility, receiving support in the form of loans and other financial services. Self-help groups (SHGs) without bank accounts face unique challenges and limitations, yet they can still be effective vehicles for community development and empowerment (Sarkar, Lakra, & Gupta (2024). These groups rely primarily on the interpersonal trust and mutual cooperation of their members. Without formal financial inclusion, they utilize informal methods of savings and credit, such as rotating savings and credit associations (ROSCAs), where members contribute regularly to a common fund that is then distributed on a rotating basis. Moreover, the lack of a bank account can inhibit the credibility and visibility of SHGs when approaching governmental or non-governmental organizations for support or grants. Despite these challenges, self-help groups without bank accounts cultivate trust and communal solidarity but often do so at the expense of growth and financial stability (Singh & Kundu, 2021, Nandal & Hooda, 2015).

References

1. Government of India, Annual Report, 2023-24, National Institute of Rural Development and Panchayati Raj, Ministry of Rural Development.
2. Government of India, Annual Report, 2024-25, National Institute of Rural Development and Panchayati Raj, Ministry of Rural Development.
3. Gothwal P. Siwach, M. (2023). Livelihood Promotion through National Rural Livelihood Mission: Path Ahead. *International Journal of Business Management and Research*. 13 (1), pp-98-104.
4. Impact of National Rural Livelihoods Mission on Rural Women - Sambodhi." *sambodhi.co.in*, 12. July 2023, <https://sambodhi.co.in/impact-of-national-rural-livelihoods-mission-on-rural-women/>. Accessed 29. Apr 2025.
5. Nandal S. Hooda, S. (2015). Progress and Performance of Self Help Group in Haryana. *International Research Journal of Commerce and Science*, 6 (10), pp-80-93.
6. Press Information Bureau (PIB). 2024. Achievements under Deendayal Antuodaya Yojana – National Livelihood Mission. Ministry of Rural Development, Government of India.
7. Sarkar. S.Lakra, S. Gupta, P.R.K. (2024), Effectiveness of National Rural Livelihood Mission Schemes on the Performance of Self-Help Group, *International Journal of Process Management and Benchmarking*, 16 (1), PP.19-35. <https://pib.gov.in/Press Release Page.aspx?PRID=2043778>.
8. Self help groups, microfinance, financial inclusion and social exclusion: Insight from Assam - PMC." *pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov*, 23. May 2023, <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10238733/>. Accessed 29. Apr 2025.
9. Singh A. Kundu, S. (2021). National Rural Livelihood Mission: Empowering Women in India. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, 12 (7), pp-7498-7509.